

1 **When Coverage Is High: Rethinking the Role of Caregiver Perceptions in Childhood**
2 **Vaccination Uptake in Uganda**

3
4 Annika K. Gunderson^{1,2*}, Taeim Kwon³, Yohhan Kumarasinghe³, Yuanyuan Yan³, Joyce Choe³,
5 Qikai Jiang³, Emmanuel Baguma⁴, Shem Bwambale⁵, John R. Barber^{2,6}, Raquel Reyes⁷, Moses
6 Ntaro⁴, Paul L. Delamater^{2,8}, Edgar M. Mulogo⁴, and Ross M. Boyce^{1,2,9}
7
8

9 ¹ Department of Epidemiology, Gillings School of Global Public Health, University of North
10 Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, North Carolina, 27599, USA
11

12 ² Carolina Population Center, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, North
13 Carolina, 27599, USA
14

15 ³ Department of Biostatistics, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, North
16 Carolina, 27599, USA
17

18 ⁴ Department of Community Health, Faculty of Medicine, Mbarara University of Science &
19 Technology, Mbarara, Uganda
20

21 ⁵ Bugoye Level III Health Center, Uganda Ministry of Health, Bugoye, Uganda
22

23 ⁶ Department of Hospital Medicine, Northern Light Mercy Hospital, Portland, Maine, 04102, USA
24

25 ⁷ Division of Hospital Medicine, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, North
26 Carolina, 27599, USA
27

28 ⁸ Department of Geography and Environment, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill,
29 Chapel Hill, North Carolina, 27599, USA
30

31 ⁹ Institute for Global Health and Infectious Diseases, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill,
32 Chapel Hill, North Carolina, 27599, USA
33
34
35

36 *Corresponding Author: e-mail: agunderson@unc.edu
37
38

39 **Word Counts:** Abstract: 200 | Text: 3267
40

41 **Running Title:** Beliefs and Experiences around Vaccination
42

43 **Citation:** Annika K Gunderson, Taeim Kwon, Yohhan Kumarasinghe, Yuanyuan Yan, Joyce
44 Choe, Qikai Jiang, Emmanuel Baguma, Shem Bwambale, John R Barber, Raquel Reyes,
45 Moses Ntaro, Paul L Delamater, Edgar M Mulogo, Ross M Boyce, When coverage is high:
46 rethinking the role of caregiver perceptions in childhood vaccination uptake in
47 Uganda, *Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 2026;
48 trag045, <https://doi.org/10.1093/trstmh/traq045>

49 **ABSTRACT**

50 **Background:** Beliefs of a child's primary caregiver are known to influence immunization uptake.
51 As coverage increases, the characteristics of households with under-vaccinated children may
52 be shifting.

53 **Methods:** We conducted a cross-sectional survey of households with a child aged 12–23
54 months. Vaccine status was verified by inspection of immunization cards or caregiver report.
55 Composite scores captured caregiver beliefs and experiences with vaccination. Associations
56 between these measures and vaccination status were evaluated using weighted logistic
57 regression.

58 **Results:** Caregivers of 1,689 children were surveyed. The odds of full vaccination were not
59 associated with composite beliefs (aOR 1.04, 95% CI: 0.95–1.14) or experiences scores (aOR
60 1.04, 95% CI: 0.96–1.13). Specific beliefs that vaccines prevent severe disease (aOR 2.68, 95%
61 CI: 1.64–4.37) and protect the community (aOR 1.67, 95% CI: 1.10–2.53) were positively
62 associated, whereas beliefs that children receive too many vaccines (aOR 0.60, 95% CI: 0.44–
63 0.83) were negatively associated with full vaccination. Positive experiences, including knowing
64 someone affected by a vaccine-preventable disease (aOR 2.10, 95% CI: 1.47–3.00), were also
65 linked to full vaccination.

66 **Conclusions:** Although composite scores were not associated with immunization status,
67 individual beliefs and experiences may still factor into caregiver decisions to vaccinate their
68 children.

69

70 **Key Words:** Africa South of the Sahara, Cross-Sectional Studies, Measles Vaccine,
71 Patient Beliefs, Uganda, Vaccination

72

73 Introduction

74 Over the past two decades, Uganda has made progress towards increasing immunization
75 access and uptake [1]. National reports indicate coverage rates between 86% and 96% for
76 childhood vaccines recommended by the Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) [2].
77 These vaccination rates exceed the 2022 regional average for sub-Saharan Africa of 72% for
78 tetanus and 69% for measles, reflecting a significant policy and health system achievement [3].
79 However, subnational heterogeneity in coverage persists. Recent analyses show vaccination
80 rates vary widely by region, household wealth, maternal education, and urban-rural location,
81 with some areas reporting full immunization coverage as low as 17% and others above 70% [4–
82 6]. In particular, challenges have been noted in rural areas with high dropout rates for later
83 doses of multidose sequences for vaccines such as pneumococcal and rotavirus, with
84 completion rates as low as 8% in some areas in 2019 [5].

85 The beliefs of caregivers, who make healthcare decisions for the child such as their guardians
86 or parents, about childhood vaccination have been shown to influence routine immunization
87 uptake in Uganda [7,8]. In particular, perceptions of vaccine safety, trust in health systems, and
88 positive prior experiences with immunization services can shape vaccine-seeking behavior. In
89 contrast, misinformation and fears of side-effects and pain during injection can discourage
90 vaccine-seeking [8–11]. In prior studies, caregivers in rural south-west Uganda have expressed
91 concerns about vaccine safety driven by known and anticipated adverse effects and beliefs that
92 vaccines are profit-driven, while also indicating a general distrust of Western healthcare [8,10].

93 Prior studies have documented negative caregiver perceptions and vaccine hesitancy in specific
94 contexts, including rural south-west Uganda, however, less is known about how these factors
95 shape behaviors in the current landscape of higher national vaccine coverage. For example, as
96 uptake increases, the distribution and characteristics of households where children remain
97 under-vaccinated may change [12,13]. In particular, children being un- or under-vaccinated may
98 become less associated with structural barriers (e.g., distance to clinic, vaccine availability) and
99 more influenced by caregiver beliefs, trust in health systems, and perceptions of disease risk
100 [14,15]. Understanding these evolving dynamics is essential to designing targeted interventions
101 to close remaining gaps in immunization coverage. Therefore, this study sought to explore the
102 potential associations between caregiver beliefs and experiences with the receipt of
103 recommended childhood immunizations.

104 Methods

105 *Study Area*

106 This study was conducted in Bugoye sub-county, located in the Kasese District of rural western
107 Uganda. The sub-county, bordering with the Democratic Republic of Congo (**Figure 1**), is
108 comprised of five parishes including Ibanda, Kibirizi, Bugoye, Muhambo, and Katooke. The area
109 sits in the foothills of the Rwenzori Mountains and is marked by steep mountain sides and large
110 changes in elevation ranging from 1 200 to 2 000 meters which can lead to variation in access
111 to health care across communities. At the time of the study, there were an estimated 6 872
112 households in Bugoye sub-county of which an estimated 15–25% had a child aged 12 to 23
113 months [16].

114

115

116

117 Figure 1. *Bugoye sub-county*. This map shows the location of parishes that compose Bugoye sub-county as well as
118 the government health facilities in the area. This map was created using QGIS with Ugandan administrative
119 shapefiles from the Humanitarian Data Exchange.

120

121 There is one level III health facility located in the Bugoye parish, while the other four parishes
122 each have a level II government health facility. In addition, there is a second level III health
123 facility in Ibanda parish that is private-not for profit. All of these facilities administer all childhood
124 vaccines.

125 *Study Design and Data Collection*

126 The study protocol detailing data collection has been previously published [16]. In brief, we
127 conducted a cross-sectional study in which all households in the Bugoye sub-county with a child
128 aged 12 to 23 months were eligible to participate. Study staff assisted by community health
129 workers visited households across all five parishes. After consent was provided, an interviewer
130 administered surveys, both of which were conducted in the local language. Surveys included
131 questions on caregiver and child demographics, attitudes and beliefs about vaccines, prior
132 experiences with vaccines and vaccination, prior hospitalization of the child and related data,
133 and vaccination status (Supplementary Material). If an adult caregiver was not available at the
134 time of visit, three more attempts were made prior to excluding the household.

135 Vaccine status was discerned by visual inspection of immunization cards. These cards are
136 distributed at local health facilities when children present for their first vaccination and are a
137 record of all vaccines received, including vaccine type and administration date. In the event the

138 children did not have their vaccine card, we asked the parent to self-report receipt of each
 139 vaccine.

140 *Outcome and Exposures*

141 The primary outcome of interest was receipt of recommended vaccines specific to the child's
 142 age at the time of the visit. A fully vaccinated child was defined as those children who received
 143 all eight recommended childhood vaccines including the tuberculosis, polio, two doses for
 144 rotavirus, measles vaccines and 3 doses of the combination vaccine for diphtheria, tetanus,
 145 pertussis, hepatitis B, and Haemophilus influenzae type b. Children considered not fully
 146 vaccinated are those missing at least one of the included vaccinations. Vaccination status for
 147 measles alone was the secondary outcome. Both outcomes were coded as binary variables.

148 Explanatory variables were (i) caregiver beliefs and (ii) previous experience or knowledge about
 149 vaccines. Responses were aggregated by domain to generate summary scores as outlined in
 150 **Table 1**. All component questions were coded to have the same valence, and aggregate scores
 151 were then calculated as the sum of the component questions answered indicating presence of
 152 the belief or experience. Secondary outcomes included each component of the aggregate belief
 153 and experience scores assessed independently.

Table 1. *Vaccination Beliefs and Experience Component Questions*

Category	Component questions
Beliefs/Attitudes	Children get more vaccinations than are good for them (B1)
	Healthy children do not need immunizations (B2)
	Vaccination does more good than harm (B3)
	It is better for a child to develop immunity by getting sick than to get a vaccination (B4)
	Parents should be allowed to selectively choose the vaccines which they believe their child needs (B5)
	It is better for a child to receive two injectable vaccinations in 1 visit rather than 1 injectable vaccination in 2 visits (B6)
	Many of the illness which vaccinations prevent are severe (B7)
	When a parent refuses to vaccinate a child, it harms the entire community through risk of disease (B8)
	People in this community have expressed concerns that a child might have a serious side effect from a vaccination (B9)
	Following the nationally recommended vaccination schedule is a good idea for a child (B10)
Experiences	If the national immunization policy states that 2 injectable vaccines should be given in the same arm/leg, would you allow it? (E1)
	I believe vaccines are safe (E2)
	I believe vaccines protect my child from vaccine preventable disease (E3)
	Have you personally seen someone with either polio, pneumonia, measles or whooping cough? (E4)
	Do you know of someone in your family or community who had either polio, pneumonia, measles or whooping cough? (E5)
	Have you ever delayed having your child get a vaccination for reasons other than illness or allergy? (E6)
	Have you ever decided not to have your child get a vaccination for reasons other than illness or allergy? (E7)
	If you had another infant today, would you want your infant to get all recommended vaccinations? (E8)
	Do you know the location where you can have your child vaccinated? (E9)
	Do you know the days and times when vaccination services are offered in your community? (E10)
	Is access to immunization easy? (E11)

	If you have to spend more than one hour getting a vaccine, are you willing to take the time because you think it is an important vaccine? (E12)
	Are you able to discuss any concerns you have about vaccinations with your child's healthcare provider? (E13)
	Do you trust the information that you receive from your local healthcare worker about vaccinations? (E14)

This table includes survey questions used to assess beliefs and attitudes and experiences with vaccination. These questions serve as the components for each aggregated score. Belief and attitude questions were measured using disagree/agree/not sure response options. Experience questions were measured using yes/no/not sure response options.

154

155 *Analysis*

156 This study is a secondary analysis of data collected to assess areas of low vaccination to
 157 develop methods to target underserved populations. We generated summary statistics for key
 158 variables, including the primary outcome of full vaccination status, and secondary outcomes
 159 such as immunization card availability and, if unavailable, self-reported vaccination status. Main
 160 predictors—continuous or ordinal scores for positive beliefs and vaccination experience—were
 161 summarized alongside potential confounders, which included caregiver characteristics, child
 162 anthropometric measures, vaccination location, and childbirth-related variables. The
 163 confounding variables were identified using prior knowledge, and the associations between
 164 each possible confounding variable and outcome or aggregated scores were tested with Chi-
 165 square tests, Wilcoxon rank-sum tests, Kendall's tau tests, and Kruskal-Wallis tests. All
 166 statistical tests were performed at a two-sided significance level of 0.05.

167 To assess caregiver and child factors associated with aggregate belief and experience scores,
 168 we used nonparametric tests. The Kendall's Tau rank correlation test was used to assess
 169 associations between continuous factors and aggregate scores. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum test
 170 and Cohen's d statistic were used to assess associations between binary factors and aggregate
 171 scores. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to assess associations between factors of more than
 172 two levels and aggregate scores. Dunn's test was used to examine multiple comparisons
 173 between groups that differed in mean rank score, and the significance level was adjusted using
 174 Holm's method to control the Type 1 error rate.

175 In our aggregated score, the more vaccine-positive response was assigned a score of 1, the
 176 less vaccine-positive response was assigned a score of 0, and responses which expressed
 177 uncertainty were assigned a score of 0.5. A weighted logistic regression was fitted for a primary
 178 outcome, fully vaccinated status, to obtain adjusted odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals. A
 179 weighted random forest was then implemented to compare performance against the weighted
 180 logistic regression after splitting the dataset into a train set (80%) and test set (20%). The
 181 evaluation metrics included receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, area under the curve
 182 (AUC), and Kappa. Although the weighted random forest outperformed the weighted logistic
 183 regression, the performance improvement over weighted logistic regression was modest
 184 (**Figure S1**). Given our focus on interpretability, we chose to use weighted logistic regression.
 185 After adjusting confounding variables identified from the exploratory analysis, our final model is
 186 given below. Categorical variables with multiple levels were included in the model using indicator
 187 variables, with one level (level 0) of each variable treated as the reference category.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{logit}(\text{Pr}(\text{Vaccination Status}_i = 1)) \\
& = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Belief Score}_i + \beta_2 \text{Experience Score}_i \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^4 \beta_{3j} 1(\text{Main Vaccination Location}_i = j) \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{4j} 1(\text{Education}_i = j) + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{5j} 1(\text{Marital Status}_i = j) \\
& + \beta_6 1(\text{Bed Net}_i = 1) + \beta_7 1(\text{Inpatient}_i = 1)
\end{aligned}$$

To account for recall bias among individuals without immunization cards, sensitivity analysis was conducted by performing these analyses exclusively on data from those with immunization cards (67% of the total sample size).

196

197 Results

198 Study Population

199 Between January 20th, 2021 and April 30th, 2021, 1 689 children were enrolled. Immunization
200 cards were available for inspection for the majority of children (1 072, 66.5%). Of those children,
201 78 were missing data regarding their vaccination status and were excluded from analyses using
202 full vaccination as the outcome. An additional 212 children were missing data on at least one
203 vaccine and but reported that child received most but not all vaccines and were excluded only
204 from the measles specific analysis if the vaccine missing data was specifically for the measles
205 vaccine. A further 6 children had unknown vaccination status for measles and were excluded
206 from the measles specific analysis.

207 Most children, 85.7% (1 381 of 1 611 children) were considered fully vaccinated. This included
208 96.5% (1 035 of 1 072 children) of those with an immunization card, but only 57.3% (309 of 539
209 children) of those without their immunization card (**Table 2**). The measles vaccine had the
210 greatest variability with 97.5% (1 111 of 1 139) of children having been vaccinated specifically
211 for measles, though 32.6% (543 of 1 689 children) of data for this vaccine were missing and
212 was thus unknown. Vaccines were received at a level III government health center and level II
213 health facility for 25.8% (415 of 1 608 children) and 39.8% (640 of 1 608 children) of children,
214 respectively with 26.4% (425 of 1 608 children) having been vaccinated at a private facility. A
215 breakdown of the study population by vaccination for each individual vaccine is available in
216 **Table S1**.

Table 2. Characteristics of Study Population

	Fully Vaccinated* (n, %)	Not Fully Vaccinated* (n, %)	Total population (n, %)
Number of Children	1381 (85.7)	230 (14.3)	1611
Parish of Residence			
Bugoye	298 (87.7)	42 (12.3)	340 (21.1)
Ibanda	387 (89.4)	46 (10.6)	433 (26.9)

Katooke	337 (87.5)	48 (12.5)	385 (23.9)
Kibirizi	122 (91.7)	11 (8.3)	133 (8.3)
Muhambo	236 (74.0)	83 (26.0)	319 (19.8)
Missing	1	0	1
Caregiver Sex			
Male	173 (78.3)	48 (21.7)	221 (13.8)
Female	1204 (86.9)	182 (13.1)	1386 (86.2)
Missing	4	0	4
Relationship of Consenting Caregiver to the child			
Mother	1136 (88.3)	151 (11.7)	1287 (80.3)
Father	147 (79.9)	37 (20.1)	184 (11.5)
Grandparent	53 (70.7)	22 (29.3)	75 (4.7)
Aunt or Uncle	27 (69.2)	12 (30.8)	39 (2.4)
Other	11 (64.7)	6 (35.3)	17 (1.1)
Missing	7	2	9
Caregiver Education			
No School	115 (76.2)	36 (23.8)	151 (9.4)
Primary School	839 (86.0)	137 (14.0)	976 (60.7)
Secondary School	389 (87.6)	55 (12.4)	444 (27.6)
University	36 (94.7)	2 (5.3)	38 (2.4)
Missing	2	0	2
Caregiver Marital Status			
Unmarried	65 (80.2)	16 (19.8)	81 (5.0)
Married	1273 (86.7)	196 (13.3)	1469 (91.2)
Divorced	36 (70.6)	15 (29.4)	51 (3.2)
Widowed	7 (77.8)	2 (22.2)	9 (0.6)
Missing	0	1	2
Number of Children in the home			
No children	15 (88.2)	2 (11.8)	17 (1.1)
1 to 2 children	484 (86.3)	77 (13.7)	561 (35.3)
3 to 5 children	571 (87.8)	79 (12.2)	650 (40.8)
6 to 10 children	275 (80.6)	66 (19.4)	341 (21.3)
More than 10 children	22 (91.7)	2 (8.3)	24 (1.5)
Missing	14	4	18
If the child was born at home			
No	738 (85.1)	129 (14.9)	867 (55.3)
Yes	607 (86.7)	93 (13.3)	700 (44.7)
Missing	36	8	44
Age of oldest child			
Mean (SD)	9.94 (7.76)	10.76 (8.60)	10.06 (7.88)
Missing	34	8	42
Location where the child was vaccinated			
Government Health Center 3	340 (81.9)	75 (18.1)	415 (25.8)
Government Health Center 2	545 (85.2)	95 (14.8)	640 (39.8)
Private Health Center or Hospital	377 (88.7)	48 (11.3)	425 (26.4)
Visit by Immunization Program	68 (88.3)	9 (11.7)	77 (4.8)
Other	49 (96.1)	2 (3.9)	51 (3.2)
Missing	2	1	3
Child's Immunization Card Availability			
Yes	1035 (96.5)	37 (3.5)	1072 (66.5)
No	309 (57.3)	230 (42.7)	539 (33.5)
Missing	0	0	0

Children were divided into fully vaccinated, having all recommended vaccines in Uganda in 2022, and not fully vaccinated, missing at least one of the recommended vaccines. Values represent the count and percentage of applicable children and means and standard deviation (SD) for continuous values. Missing values are excluded from percentage calculations.

* Fully vaccinated and not fully vaccinated columns use row percentages while the total column uses column percentages.

218 *Aggregate Belief and Experience Scores*

219 Neither aggregate scores for caregiver beliefs nor experiences suggest a higher odds of a child
220 being fully vaccinated for each additional positive belief (aOR 1.04, 95% CI: 0.95, 1.14) and
221 experience (aOR 1.04, 95% CI: 0.96, 1.13) compared to children who were not fully vaccinated
222 after adjusting for vaccination location, caregiver education, caregiver marital status, LLIN use,
223 and history of hospitalization for malaria (**Figure 2**).

224

225
226 *Figure 2. Forest Plots of the Association between Vaccination Status and Composite Scores* Forest plot odds ratio of
227 the log scale for comparisons of (A) children considered fully vaccinated versus not fully vaccinated and (B) children
228 with the measles vaccine compared to those without the measles vaccine. Both panels include ORs for the composite
229 scores. Children with data on overall vaccination status but not individual vaccines were still included in panel A. Dots
230 on each bar indicate the point estimate and the 95% confidence interval represented by the bars extending from the
231 point estimate.
232

233 When considering the measles vaccine alone, positive experiences with vaccines were found to
234 have a positive association with vaccination (aOR: 1.10, 95% CI: (0.82, 1.48)) (**Figure 2**).
235 However, more positive belief scores were associated with lower odds of vaccination (aOR:
236 0.54, 95% CI: (0.39, 0.73)).

237 *Individual Belief and Experiences*

238 Of individual belief components, agreeing with the statement “Children get more vaccinations
239 than are good for them” was strongly associated with a lower odds of a caregiver’s child being
240 fully vaccinated (aOR 0.60, 95% CI: 0.44, 0.83) (**Figure 3**). In contrast, agreement with the
241 statements “Many of the illness which vaccinations prevent are severe” or “When a parent
242 refuses to vaccinate a child, it harms the entire community through risk of disease” was
243 associated with higher odds of a caregiver’s child being fully vaccinated with adjusted ORs of
244 2.68 (95% CI: (1.64, 4.37)) and 1.67 (95% CI: (1.10, 2.53)), respectively. All other individual
245 beliefs and attitudes were not statistically associated with receipt of all vaccinations.

246

247

248 Figure 3. *Forest Plots of the Association between Vaccination Status and Score Components* Forest plots show the
 249 odds ratios of the log scale for comparisons of (A) individual experience questions and (B) individual belief questions
 250 with child vaccination status (fully vaccinated versus not fully vaccinated). Children with data on overall vaccination
 251 status but not individual vaccines were still included in both panels. Dots on each bar indicate the point estimate and
 252 the 95% confidence interval represented by the bars extending from the point estimate.
 253

254 Regarding individual experiences, prior delay of a child's vaccination for reasons other than
 255 allergy or illness was associated with lower odds of a caregiver's child being fully vaccinated
 256 (aOR 0.34, 95% CI: 0.24, 0.48). Being able to discuss any concerns with a child's healthcare
 257 provider or knowing a person who had either polio, pneumonia, measles, or whooping cough
 258 was associated with a 2.44 (95% CI: 1.35, 4.41) and 2.10 (95% CI: (1.47, 3.00)) times higher
 259 odds of a caregiver's child being fully vaccinated respectively. All other individual experiences
 260 were not statistically associated with receipt of all vaccinations. Descriptive details on individual
 261 attitude/beliefs and experience by vaccination status are included in **Table S2**.

262

263 *Factors Associated with Belief and Experience Scores*

264 Several factors were found to be associated with aggregate belief scores including caregiver
 265 education, facility type visited for vaccination, the facility type where the child was born, and if
 266 the child slept under an LLIN. Bringing their child to government health centers or attended
 267 immunization visits to receive vaccinations was associated with a higher aggregate belief score
 268 compared to those visiting private facilities (**Table 3**). Caregivers who did not complete school
 269 were the most likely to have a lower aggregate belief score compared to those who completed
 270 primary or secondary school. Further, caregivers of children born at home or government health
 271 facilities were more likely to have a higher aggregate belief score over care givers using private
 272 clinics or hospitals. Children who slept under a bed net in the previous night were associated
 273 with a higher aggregate belief score.

Table 3. Caregiver and Child Factors Associated with Aggregate Belief and Experience Scores

	Belief Score		Experience Score	
	Effect size	p-value	Effect size	p-value
Number of children living in the home	-0.001	0.946	0.070	<0.001 ***
If the child slept under an LLIN the previous night	0.089	<0.001 ***	0.006	0.808
If the child has ever been hospitalized	0.003	0.623	0.131	<0.001 ***
Primary vaccination location		<0.001 ***		0.002 **
Govt. Health Center 2 vs. Private Health Center or Hospital	130	<0.001 ***	68.8	0.137
Govt. Health Center 3 vs. Private Health Center or Hospital	158	<0.001 ***	-40.2	1.00
Visit by Immunization Program vs. Private Health Center or Hospital	224	<0.001 ***	-46.5	1.00
Visit by Immunization Program vs. Other	242	0.02 *	-38.2	1.00
Govt. Health Center 2 vs. Govt. Health Center 3	27.3	0.696	109	<0.001 ***
Education level of the caregiver		0.006 **		0.019 *
No school vs. Primary school	-138	<0.001 ***	103	0.04 *
No school vs. Secondary school	-132	0.01 *	129	0.01 *
Marital status of the caregiver		0.396		0.002 **
Married vs. Unmarried	82.8	0.714	182.4	0.003 **
Where the child born		<0.001 ***		0.833
Home vs. Private clinic or Hospital	102	0.003 **	-15.2	1.00
Government Health Facility vs. Private Clinic or Hospital	114	<0.001 ***	-2.32	0.927

The Kendall's Tau rank correlation test was used to assess an association between the number of children living in the home and aggregate score. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum test and Cohen's d statistic were used to assess whether a child who slept under an LLIN the previous night or had ever been hospitalized was associated with aggregate score. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to assess whether primary vaccination location, caregiver education level, caregiver marital status, or child

birthplace was associated with aggregate score. Dunn's test was used to perform multiple comparisons and calculate mean rank differences. The significance level (α) was adjusted to 0.05 using Holm's method.

Note: (*) is used to indicate $p < 0.05$, ** for $p < 0.01$, and *** for $p < 0.001$

274

275 In contrast, higher experience scores were associated with a larger number of children living in
 276 the home, if a child had previously stayed overnight in a hospital or clinic compared to those
 277 never spending a night in a hospital, and married caregivers compared to unmarried caregivers.
 278 Similar to higher belief scores, higher experience scores were also associated with caregivers
 279 bringing their child to government health centers for vaccinations. In contrast to belief score,
 280 caregivers who did not complete school compared to those who completed primary and
 281 secondary school were associated with a higher aggregate experience score.

282 *Factors Associated with Immunization Card Reports*

283 Caregiver sex, relationship to child, marital status, education level, and bed net use were
 284 significantly associated with immunization card reports (**Table 4**). Among households with child
 285 immunization cards, caregivers were 1.30 times as likely to be female than male. Additionally,
 286 mothers were more likely to show immunization cards than fathers, grandparents, aunts, uncles,
 287 and other caregivers (RR = 1.28, 1.77, 1.70, 2.17). Households with bed nets were 1.43 times
 288 as likely to show immunization cards than those without bed nets.

Table 4. Caregiver Characteristics Associated with Immunization Card Reports

	Has Immunization Card (n, %)	No Immunization Card (n, %)	p-value ¹
	1138 (67.8)	541 (32.2)	
Caregiver sex			< 0.001 ***
Female	1010 (69.9)	435 (30.1)	
Male	124 (53.9)	106 (46.1)	
Missing	4	0	
Relationship to Child			< 0.001 ***
Mother	970 (72.2)	374 (27.8)	
Father	108 (56.3)	84 (43.8)	
Grandparent	31 (40.8)	45 (59.2)	
Aunt or Uncle	17 (42.5)	23 (57.5)	
Other	6 (33.3)	12 (66.7)	
Missing	6	3	
Education level of the caregiver			0.003 **
No school	87 (55.4)	70 (44.6)	
Primary school	699 (68.4)	323 (31.6)	
Secondary school	319 (69.5)	140 (30.5)	
University	31 (79.5)	8 (20.5)	
Missing	2	0	
Marital status of the caregiver			0.002 **
Unmarried	46 (54.8)	38 (45.2)	
Married	1057 (69.1)	473 (30.9)	
Divorced	27 (50.9)	26 (49.1)	
Widowed	7 (70.0)	3 (30.0)	
Missing	1	1	
LLIN Use			< 0.001 ***
Yes	1068 (69.5)	469 (30.5)	
No	68 (48.6)	72 (51.4)	
Missing	2	0	

¹Pearson's Chi-squared test; Fisher's exact test.

289

290 *Sensitivity Analysis*

291 The sensitivity analysis assessing the impact of having a vaccine card versus incorporating
292 caregiver recall produced similar results to the primary analysis. However, differences exist
293 between the two groups. In the model for vaccine card availability, caregivers with a secondary
294 level education, being married, and use of an LLIN for the child were more likely to have a
295 vaccine card available for inspection. Importantly, vaccine card presence was significantly
296 associated with positive caregiver experiences as an aggregated score. Further details are
297 available in the supplementary material and **Figure S2**.

298 **Discussion**

299 In this cross-sectional survey of rural villages in western Uganda, we found that approximately
300 85% of children were fully vaccinated – a proportion similar to or slightly higher than the national
301 average and notable for rural settings, where coverage is often more variable. We did see
302 positive associations between vaccination status and (i) caregiver beliefs or experiences relating
303 to vaccine-preventable diseases and (ii) perceptions of community benefit. In contrast, children
304 of caregivers who expressed concerns about the number of vaccines children receive and those
305 who had previously delayed vaccines for non-medical reasons were less likely to be fully
306 vaccinated. However, we did not find statistical associations between vaccination status and the
307 belief or experience composite scores.

308 The lack of association with composite scores, alongside significant effects for individual beliefs
309 and experiences indicates that overall caregiver attitudes may matter less than particular
310 concerns in shaping vaccination behavior. Further, in a relatively high-coverage setting, broad
311 caregiver belief and experience measures may have limited ability to explain differences in
312 vaccination status, and variation is instead concentrated among a smaller subgroup with
313 specific concerns. This may partly be attributed to vaccination being generally accepted in this
314 setting, so most caregivers vaccinate their children by default, highlighting the importance of
315 examining specific beliefs and experiences when designing interventions.

316 From a programmatic perspective, this suggests that interventions based on generalized
317 vaccine promotion or confidence-building may yield diminishing returns in similar settings.
318 Instead, more targeted strategies, such as addressing concerns about vaccination schedules,
319 engaging caregivers who have previously delayed vaccination, and working to strengthen
320 continuity of care, may be more effective in reaching the remaining under-vaccinated children.

321 Evidence from other sub-Saharan African settings suggests that as vaccination coverage
322 increases and access improves, under-vaccination becomes less associated with physical
323 barriers and more influenced by caregiver beliefs, trust in the health system, and perceptions of
324 disease risk [14,17,18]. Our findings diverge somewhat from this expectation. This may reflect
325 that high baseline coverage compresses variability in general attitudes, leaving only specific
326 beliefs or system factors to influence uptake. Instead, what we observe may reflect an overall
327 high level of vaccine confidence in Uganda, where – at least prior to the COVID-19 pandemic -

328 84% of the population believed vaccines are safe, 83% considered them effective, and 76%
329 viewed childhood vaccination as important, which leaves little room for perception-related
330 variation in uptake [19]. It may also be that beliefs and attitudes around vaccination work in
331 conjunction with other factors not considered in our study such as familial support and
332 community ties and values [20,21].

333 However, receipt of the measles vaccine was associated with the more negative beliefs about
334 vaccines. This finding should be interpreted with caution. In sensitivity analyses including only
335 children with an immunization card, the association of full vaccination status with belief score
336 was positive, suggesting that the observed relationship in the full sample may be driven by
337 differences in measurement between caregivers with and without immunization cards.

338 These findings may also be explained by differences between those who maintained their
339 immunization cards and those that did not, by programmatic and supply-side challenges rather
340 than caregiver hesitancy or a combination of both factors. Even when caregivers are motivated
341 and supportive, vaccine uptake can be hindered by stockouts or shortages of the measles
342 vaccine at health facilities, a documented issue in Uganda though not specific to the measles
343 vaccine [22]. Alternatively, these results could be influenced by social desirability bias,
344 participants may be reluctant to express negative views of government health services or
345 vaccination, potentially leading to over-reported confidence in vaccines. This association could
346 also result from uncontrolled confounding. Similar contradictory relationships have been
347 reported in other sub-Saharan African settings where full vaccination was found to be
348 associated with worse health service delivery [20]. In summary, these findings suggest that the
349 observed negative association is unlikely to reflect a true inverse relationship between caregiver
350 beliefs and vaccination uptake, but rather highlights the influence of measurement limitations
351 and health system factors. This supports our broader finding that, in relatively high-coverage
352 settings, residual variation in vaccination may be driven less by caregiver beliefs and more by
353 challenges related to competing the immunization schedule.

354 Overall, the caregivers who take their children to a government health facility or immunization
355 program, had completed primary or secondary school, and delivered their children at a
356 government health facility tended to have more positive beliefs about vaccination. These
357 findings are consistent with other studies demonstrating that maternal education, facility-based
358 delivery, and engagement with routine health services are strongly associated with greater
359 vaccine confidence and uptake [23,24]. In addition, presenting the immunization card was more
360 common among female caregivers, most often the mother, and those with higher education,
361 who may also have the ability to take greater care with other health-related behaviors, such as
362 proper use of LLINs, reflecting overall health consciousness [25].

363 Beliefs around vaccines preventing severe disease and harms of vaccine refusal to the
364 community as well as the ability to discuss concerns with healthcare providers and knowing
365 someone who had previously been infected with a vaccine preventable disease including polio,
366 pneumonia, measles, or whooping cough was associated with a higher odds of a caregiver's
367 child being fully vaccinated This is in line with other studies that demonstrate how caregiver
368 awareness of disease severity and perceived benefits of vaccination are key drivers of vaccine
369 uptake. In rural areas of western Uganda, mothers who demonstrated a basic understanding of

370 the importance of childhood immunizations were more likely to ensure their children received
371 timely and complete vaccinations [24]. These findings that in high-coverage settings such as
372 ours, leveraging trusted CHWs to address specific concerns and reinforce completion of the full
373 vaccination schedule may be particularly important for reaching the remaining under-vaccinated
374 children.

375 *Limitations*

376 While this study was benefited by a large sample size and a census of children from the target
377 population, a relatively large subset of children did not have an immunization card. Sensitivity
378 analyses did indicate differences in results when including the entire sample versus including
379 only caregivers with immunization cards. This difference could either be driven by recall bias or
380 systematic differences between the two groups related to card ownership. For example,
381 individuals who are more concerned with making sure their children are fully vaccinated may
382 also be more likely to retain and keep track of the immunization card. To try to assess the
383 potential impact of recall bias, we re-ran models with datasets representing 10 to 50% recall
384 bias among those without their immunization cards which show little impact on the results in
385 either magnitude or direction.

386 Additionally, due to the higher-than-expected vaccination coverage for a rural area, there was
387 little variation in outcome measures. This homogeneity limited the study's statistical power and
388 increased the risk of model instability. Given the imbalance in the outcome data, caution should
389 be taken when interpreting the results.

390 There is also a possibility of bias given the presence of CHWs during the interviews that might
391 have led participants to report more socially desirable responses regarding vaccination beliefs
392 and experiences. It is also possible that it would lead to overreporting of vaccinations, however,
393 given the ability to check vaccination cards and the results of the sensitivity analysis, we believe
394 this to be small.

395 Lastly, this study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic and attitudes towards
396 vaccination may have changed either positively or negatively in the wake of the roll out of the
397 COVID-19 vaccine.

398 **Authors' Statements**

399 *Authors' contributions*

400 RMB, PLD, and EMM conceived and designed the study; EB oversaw data collection; TK, YK,
401 YY, JC, QJ, and AKG carried out analysis and interpretation of these data. AKG, TK, YK, YY, JC,
402 and QJ drafted the manuscript; EB, SB, JB, RR, PLD, MN, EMM, and RMB critically revised the
403 manuscript for intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript. AKG and
404 RMB are guarantors of the paper.

405

406 *Acknowledgements*

407 We would like to acknowledge and thank our participants for giving their time for the completion
408 of this project. We would also like to thank all research assistants on the project for their efforts
409 in data collection.

410

411 *Funding*

412 This work was supported by a Grand Challenge Award (OPP1199232) from the Bill & Melinda
413 Gates Foundation to RMB. Database support was provided by the National Center for
414 Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS), National Institutes of Health, through Grant Award
415 Number UM1TR004406.

416

417 *Data Availability*

418 Deidentified individual data that supports the results will be made available provided the
419 investigator who proposes to use the data has approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB),
420 Independent Ethics Committee (IEC), or Research Ethics Board (REB), as applicable, and
421 executes a data use/sharing agreement with UNC. The Principal Investigator should submit a
422 request to the UNC Industry Contracting team (OSPContracting@unc.edu) to initiate the data
423 use/ sharing agreement.

424

425 *Competing interests*

426 None declared

427

428 *Ethical approval*

429 The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Mbarara University of Science and
430 Technology Research Ethics Committee (11/11-18), the Uganda National Council of Science
431 and Technology (HS 2617), and the UNC Institutional Review Board (18-2885). Written informed
432 consent was be obtained from all adult study participants and the caregivers of children.

433 **References**

- 434 1. Ssebagereka A, de Broucker G, Ekirapa-Kiracho E *et al.* Equity in vaccine coverage in
435 Uganda from 2000 to 2016: revealing the multifaceted nature of inequity. *BMC Public Health*
436 2024;**24**:185.
- 437 2. WHO Immunization Data portal - African Region. *Immunization Data*.
- 438 3. WHO Regional Office for Africa. *Ending Disease in Africa: Status of Immunization Coverage*
439 *in Africa as of the End of 2022*. Brazzaville, Congo, 2023.
- 440 4. Wasswa R, Kananura RM, Waiswa P *et al.* Subnational trends and inequalities of under-
441 immunisation and zero-dose among children aged 12–23 months in Uganda: a national
442 population-based cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open* 2025;**15**:e093619.
- 443 5. Jammeh A, Muhoozi M, Kulane A *et al.* Comparing full immunisation status of children (0-23
444 months) between slums of Kampala City and the rural setting of Iganga District in Uganda: a
445 cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Serv Res* 2023;**23**:856.
- 446 6. Uganda Bureau of Statistics, UNICEF, World Bank *et al.* Uganda Demographic and Health
447 Survey 2022. *Uganda Demographic and Health Survey 2022*. 2023.
- 448 7. Babirye JN, Engebretsen IMS, Makumbi F *et al.* Timeliness of Childhood Vaccinations in
449 Kampala Uganda: A Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study. *PLOS ONE* 2012;**7**:e35432.
- 450 8. Kigongo E, Opollo MS, Nalwoga V *et al.* Perspectives of Pediatric Vaccination Among the
451 Batwa Community in Western Uganda: A Qualitative Study. *Global Pediatric Health*
452 2024;**11**:2333794X241298834.
- 453 9. Oduwole EO, Mahomed H, Laurenzi CA *et al.* Point-of-care vaccinators' perceptions of
454 vaccine hesitancy drivers: A qualitative study from the cape metropolitan district, South Africa.
455 *Vaccine* 2021;**39**:5506–12.
- 456 10. Adeyanju GC, Sprengholz P, Betsch C *et al.* Caregivers' Willingness to Vaccinate Their
457 Children against Childhood Diseases and Human Papillomavirus: A Cross-Sectional Study on
458 Vaccine Hesitancy in Malawi. *Vaccines* 2021;**9**:1231.
- 459 11. Mavundza EJ, Cooper S, Wiysonge CS. A Systematic Review of Factors That Influence
460 Parents' Views and Practices around Routine Childhood Vaccination in Africa: A Qualitative
461 Evidence Synthesis. *Vaccines* 2023;**11**:563.
- 462 12. Ozigbu CE, Olatosi B, Li Z *et al.* Correlates of Zero-Dose Vaccination Status among
463 Children Aged 12–59 Months in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Multilevel Analysis of Individual and
464 Contextual Factors. *Vaccines (Basel)* 2022;**10**:1052.
- 465 13. Ikilezi G, Augusto OJ, Sbarra A *et al.* Determinants of geographical inequalities for DTP3
466 vaccine coverage in sub-Saharan Africa. *Vaccine* 2020;**38**:3447–54.
- 467 14. Bangura JB, Xiao S, Qiu D *et al.* Barriers to childhood immunization in sub-Saharan Africa: A
468 systematic review. *BMC Public Health* 2020;**20**:1108.

- 469 15. Fenta SM, Biresaw HB, Fentaw KD *et al.* Determinants of full childhood immunization
470 among children aged 12-23 months in sub-Saharan Africa: a multilevel analysis using
471 Demographic and Health Survey Data. *Trop Med Health* 2021;**49**:29.
- 472 16. Boyce RM, Delamater P, Muhindo R *et al.* Accessible metrics of access: Novel tools to
473 measure immunization coverage in rural sub-Saharan Africa. 2019, DOI:
474 10.12688/gatesopenres.13066.1.
- 475 17. Tamirat KS, Sisay MM. Full immunization coverage and its associated factors among
476 children aged 12–23 months in Ethiopia: further analysis from the 2016 Ethiopia demographic
477 and health survey. *BMC Public Health* 2019;**19**:1019.
- 478 18. Lakew Y, Bekele A, Biadgilign S. Factors influencing full immunization coverage among 12-
479 23 months of age children in Ethiopia: evidence from the national demographic and health
480 survey in 2011. *BMC Public Health* 2015;**15**:728.
- 481 19. Vaccine confidence in Uganda. *The Vaccine Confidence Project*.
- 482 20. Bell J, Lartey B, Fernandez M *et al.* A structural equation modelling approach to
483 understanding the determinants of childhood vaccination in Nigeria, Uganda and Guinea. *PLOS*
484 *Global Public Health* 2023;**3**:e0001289.
- 485 21. Bell J, Lartey B, Spickernell G *et al.* Applying a social-ecological model to understand factors
486 impacting demand for childhood vaccinations in Nigeria, Uganda, and Guinea. *SSM -*
487 *Qualitative Research in Health* 2022;**2**:100180.
- 488 22. Immunization and vaccine-preventable communicable diseases.
- 489 23. Fadl N, Abdelmoneim SA, Gebreal A *et al.* Routine childhood immunization in Sub-Saharan
490 Africa: addressing parental vaccine hesitancy. *Public Health* 2024;**226**:66–73.
- 491 24. Vonasek BJ, Bajunirwe F, Jacobson LE *et al.* Do Maternal Knowledge and Attitudes towards
492 Childhood Immunizations in Rural Uganda Correlate with Complete Childhood Vaccination?
493 *PLOS ONE* 2016;**11**:e0150131.
- 494 25. Li W, Sewolo F, Aoun A *et al.* Characteristics of Studies Focusing on Vaccine Series
495 Completion Among Children Aged 12–23 Months in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Scoping Review.
496 *Children* 2025;**12**:415.
- 497